

THE IMPACT OF GENETIC FACTOR ON INDIVIDUAL NUTRITIONAL NEEDS

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ABSTRACT

The impact of genetic factors on individual nutritional needs is a complex area of research that underscores the significance of genetic variations in shaping an individual's response to nutrition. Genes control the body's ability to absorb, metabolize, and utilize nutrients from the food consumed. The diversity of genetic variations among individuals can result in different nutritional requirements and predispose individuals to specific diseases and dietary issues. Through the development of nutrigenetics and nutrigenomics, scientists have identified numerous genes and genetic variations that play a crucial role in determining how the body absorbs and utilizes nutrients. This knowledge opens the door to personalized nutrition, where dietary regimens are tailored to individual genetic profiles to achieve optimal well-being and disease prevention. The influence of genetic factors on individual nutritional needs also highlights the importance of moving away from the use of universal dietary guidelines. Instead, the approach to nutrition should be customized based on each person's genetic characteristics to achieve the best possible outcomes. Despite the challenges and uncertainties in this research area, the future of nutrition appears promising, as personalized nutrition has the potential to enhance the health and well-being of people worldwide.

The aim of this paper is to explore the impact of genetic factors on individual nutritional needs and provide an overview of how genetics shapes the body's responses to nutrition, with

an emphasis on the development of personalized nutrition for better health and disease prevention.

1. INTRODUCTION

Genetic variation is a fundamental characteristic of human biological systems. These variations are responsible for various aspects of human physiology, including appearance, metabolic processes, ability to defend against disease, and the like. Genetic variation can be observed at different levels, including individual genes, entire chromosomes, and entire gene sets. Each of these variations can have different effects on human health and well-being. Genetic variation is a product of evolution and patrimony, and it is the key off understanding why people are different in their responses to the environment, including diet. Genetics and nutritionism are fields that have developed more and more in recent decades, providing a deeper understanding of the bond between genes and nutrition. This interdisciplinary field, known as nutrigenetics and nutrigenomics, investigates how genetic variation in individuals affects their response to diet, metabolic processes, and susceptibility to certain diseases. Understanding how human genes affect diet can be significant from the perspective of chronic disease prevention and treatment, personalized nutrition, and health optimization.

2. THE METHODOLOGY OF WORK CREATION

Relevant literature from the field of research on "The impact of genetic factors on individual nutritional needs" was reviewed. Literature was found in academic databases: ScienceDirect, PubMed, Web of Science. Using methods of analysis and synthesis of relevant data on key chronic non-infectious diseases through the framework of nutrigenetics and nutrigenomics, more significant aspects of the possibility of personalized nutrition were observed.

3. NUTRIGENETICS AND NUTRIGENOMICS

Nutrigenomics is a research science that studies how nutrition affects the genome and gene expression, while nutrigenetics is an applied science that studies how genotype determines an individual's response to nutrition and susceptibility to disease. According to the original conception of the author Brennan, nutrigenetics refers to the interaction between nutritional and genetic factors that may play a role in the etiology of disease. Efforts are aimed at determining increased risks of occurrence and development of chronic non-infectious diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes or psychiatric disorders, and by applying the genome-wide association studies (GWAS); linking environmental factors and genetic variation (Novaković et al. 2014). Nutrigenetics works on how an individual's genetic makeup

affects the phenotypic response to food intake. Nutrigenomics, on the other hand, focuses on gene expression with respect to nutrition. Nutrigenomics aims to investigate the impact of diet and nutrition on gene expression, particularly through epigenomic (e.g. histone methylation), transcriptomic (e.g. RNA transcription), proteomic (e.g. protein synthesis) and metabolomic (e.g. metabolite synthesis) high-throughput analysis (Simopoulos and Milner, 2010).

Through mutual interactions, nutrigenetics and nutrigenomics complement each other as a specialty of nutrigenetics/nutrigenomics to provide an overall picture of an individual's integrated metabolism, with the aim of constructing a personalized diet to avoid diseases and possible health risks and to promote health and longevity as well (Dimitrov, 2011).

3.1. Principles of nutrigenomics and nutrigenetics

The basic principles of nutrigenomics and nutrigenetics refer to the influence of macro and micronutrients on the human genome, causing changes in its structure and gene expression, which may have implications in the occurrence, frequency, progression and severity of the disease. In addition, under certain circumstances and in some individuals, nutrition can be an important risk factor for the development of numerous diseases. The extent to which diet affects on balance between health and disease may depend on an individual's genetic framework. Ultimately, nutritional intervention is based on knowledge of the nutritional status and needs of the individual, as well as the genotype, and can be used for the prevention, mitigation or treatment of chronic diseases (Novaković et al. 2014).

3.2. Personalized nutrition as a goal of nutrigenetics and nutrigenomics

Understanding how human genetic profiles affect nutritional needs enables the creation of personalized nutritional strategies that can improve quality of life and reduce the risk of chronic diseases (Corella, 2018). If the human population were genetically identical and lived in a constant environment, then the human response to diet and medication would be equivalent; however this is not the case. Inter-individual variability in response to dietary interventions is a well-known phenomenon in nutrition research and practice. Thus, the effect of dietary changes on phenotypes such as blood cholesterol level, body weight, and blood pressure can vary considerably between individuals. There are many factors that can influence dietary response, such as age, sex, physical activity, smoking and genetics (Carlberg et al. 2016). Attempts are being made to develop personalized dietary guidelines for individuals and specific subpopulations (Moschonis et al. 2019). The goal of personalized nutrition is to identify individuals who benefit from a specific nutritional intervention (responders), and to

find alternatives for those who do not (non-responders). This alternative approach to nutrition is considered more effective compared to unnecessary diets that are considered unpleasant and ineffective. Personalized nutrition can also be useful in the prevention and treatment of chronic diseases by adapting dietary advice to the unique genetic profile of each individual (Kohlmeier, 2012).

3.3. Metabolomics in the field of dietetics

Metabolomics is an area of functional genomics that studies changes in metabolites, and its goal is to isolate and characterize them. The metabolome consists of the set of small primary/secondary metabolites and body fluids of an organism or species.

In the field of nutrition, metabolomics enables the understanding of metabolic changes and disorders that are caused by or susceptible to the influence of nutrition. This contributes to the understanding of how an excess or deficiency of certain nutrients or compounds (secondary metabolites) present in food can affect the health/disease of an individual. These compounds (whether nutritional or not) interact in different ways within the body, changing the metabolic pathways of the metabolome. As an example, peryl alcohol (a monoterpene extracted from strawberries) can act as an anticancer molecule under certain organic stimuli (Weckwerth, 2007). Metabolomics is the study of the total number of endogenous and exogenous metabolites in a cell, organ or body fluids and is a useful tool for generating individual metabolite profiles, such as complete plasma lipid profiles (e.g. cholesterol, triglycerides) and vitamins.

4. INFLUENCE OF GENETIC ERRORS ON NUTRIENT METABOLISM

Metabolic processes such as digestion, absorption, and excretion are selectively affected by many different inborn errors of nutrient metabolism. More than 200 such disorders have already been described: lactose intolerance; malabsorption of glucose-galactose; familial hypercholesterolemia; hypophosphatemic rickets and others. These disorders can lead to a lack of essential nutrients despite adequate food intake; which can result in unfavorable conditions such as chemical toxicity (by blocking the catabolic pathway necessary for the metabolism of the ingested nutrient) or interfering with the formation of the necessary product from the ingested nutrient.

Genetic factors play a key role in the process of absorption of nutrients from the digestive tract. The genes responsible for the synthesis of enzymes and transport proteins in the intestines affect the ability of the body to absorb macro and micronutrients. Genetic variations

in these genes can result in different absorption rates in different individuals. Genetic variations can affect the enzymes involved in carbohydrate and fat breakdown, resulting in variations in energy balance and fat storage. Genes also influence the level and function of proteins that have roles in the regulation of glucose and insulin, and also influence the absorption, transport and metabolism of micronutrients (Ross et al. 2014):

- Absorption of iron from food is a complex process. The genes encoding the proteins ferritin and transferrin affect the storage and transport of iron in the body. Genetic variations of these genes can lead to altered levels of iron in the body and the risk of iron deficiency anemia.
- Calcium is a key mineral for bone and muscle health. Genetic variations in the genes responsible for the transport of calcium across cell membranes in the intestines can affect absorption efficiency, which means they can result in variations in calcium levels in the body.
- Genes can affect the enzymes that are responsible for the conversion of inactive forms of vitamins into their active forms. The absorption of vitamin D, which is crucial for bone health, depends on the presence of genes that code for enzymes in the liver and kidneys to convert inactive vitamin D into an active form. Genetic variations of these genes can affect the level of vitamin D in the blood.
- Vitamin B₁₂ is necessary for the normal functioning of the nervous system and the formation of red blood cells. Absorption of vitamin B₁₂ from food requires the presence of certain genes, including a gene known as IF (Intrinsic Factor). Genetic mutations that affect IF can result in disturbances in the absorption of vitamin B₁₂ and the risk of deficiency (Hansen, 2011).

5. NUTRIGENOMICS IN DISEASE ETIOLOGY AND SPECIFICATION OF NUTRITIONAL REQUIREMENTS

5.1. Gene polymorphisms associated with heart diseases with aspect on specific nutritional needs

A major locus on chromosome 9p21 was identified for coronary heart disease. The 9p21 variant is a new risk factor for coronary heart disease and cerebrovascular disease, independent of known risk factors such as diabetes, hypertension, cholesterol and obesity. This information implies a new mechanism for coronary heart disease related to vascular pathology, perhaps from the lipid hypothesis (Willis, 2020). Also, genetic variation in 5-

hipoxygenases (5-LO) play a key role in an individual's susceptibility to coronary heart disease, and the interaction between omega-6 and omega-3 fatty acids may be essential to understanding and prevention of this serious heart disease (Artemis and Leslie, 2003). 5-LO is an enzyme that participates in the metabolism of arachidonic acid and the production of inflammatory compounds. Studies have shown that people with certain genetic variants in the 5-LO gene may have an increased sensitivity to increased intake of omega-6 fatty acids, which for these people means a higher risk of inflammation if they consume large amounts of these fatty acids.

The level of omega-6 and omega-3 fatty acids in the body can be determined by genetic variations in the FADS1 and FADS2 gene clusters. Studies have shown that omega-6 fatty acids can stimulate inflammatory processes in the body, which is an important factor in the development of atherosclerosis, the basic pathology in coronary heart disease. On the other hand, omega-3 fatty acids have an anti-inflammatory effect and can reduce inflammatory reactions. Thus, some individuals may be more susceptible to atherosclerosis due to their genetic predisposition that promotes increased intake of omega-6 fatty acids, while others may have better protection against coronary heart disease due to their ability to exercise better the same omega-3 fatty acids (Artemis and Leslie, 2003).

5.1.1. APOE gene polymorphisms in the development of heart disease and nutritional specifications

The Apolipoprotein E (APOE) gene is the gene that codes for apolipoprotein E, a protein that plays a key role in lipid metabolism and lipoprotein transport in the body. The APOE gene plays a significant role in cholesterol metabolism and affects its level in the blood, and it also plays an important role in the regulation of inflammation in the body and the way the body processes lipids from food.

The APOE gene is located the chromosome 19 and exists in several different variants, the best known of which are APOE ϵ 2, APOE ϵ 3 and APOE ϵ 4. These are gene variants that affect the risk of various diseases, including cardiovascular disease and Alzheimer's disease. Each of these variants has a different effect on lipid metabolism and the way the body manipulates cholesterol. People with the APOE ϵ 2 gene variant have a lower risk of cardiovascular disease, but an increased risk of Alzheimer's disease. APOE ϵ 3 is considered the reference variant of this gene and it is also the most frequently represented variant. Its presence usually does not increase or decrease the risk of disease. People with the APOE ϵ 4 variant have an

increased risk of cardiovascular disease and Alzheimer's disease. Thus, people at high risk of Alzheimer's disease can consider specific measures to preserve a healthy brain, while people at high risk of cardiovascular disease can adjust their diet and lifestyle to reduce that risk (Brigelius-Flohé and Joost, 2006).

5.2. Nutritional needs of people with phenylketonuria

Phenylketonuria (PKU) is a disease caused by mutations in the gene for the enzyme Phenylalanine hydroxylase (PAH) which converts phenylalanine into tyrosine. PKU was the first "inborn error of metabolism" to respond to dietary treatment, using a low-phenylalanine diet regimen for nutrigenetic treatment. Genetic variations in phenylalanine hydroxylase can lead to a reduction of its activity or insufficiency of this enzyme, which leads to elevated concentrations of phenylalanine in the blood, which crosses the blood-brain barrier and damages brain function. When phenylalanine is broken down by other metabolic pathways, phenylketones are formed, which are also neurotoxic so people with a PKU can develop neurological damage (severe mental retardation and seizures) (Marinović, 2019).

Dietary measures for people with a PKU refer to diet with a low intake of phenylalanine and taking supplements of other amino acids that enable normal development of the child. In this context, it is necessary to detect PKU by newborn screening in order to start a child with a low phenylalanine content as early as possible.

5.3. Interactions of genes and nutrients in the etiology of cancer

Twin studies show that the probability of identical twins developing the same cancer is less than 10%, suggesting that environment plays an important role in cancer susceptibility. Evidence of genome and epigenome damage as biomarkers, in the absence of exposure to genotoxins, are themselves sensitive indicators of micronutrient deficiencies required as cofactors or components of DNA repair enzymes. Diet is considered a source of carcinogens present in certain foods and their ingredients. Some food components, such as phytoestrogens, are known to be processed by the same metabolic pathways as sex hormones, so their action can be modulated by polymorphisms (George et al. 2011). Molecules present in contaminated food can create toxic metabolites that can interact with DNA, changing its structure and causing mutations. This is the case with aflatoxin B₁, which creates an additional compound capable of binding to the N-7 position of guanine residues, creating a new product. This new molecule then breaks the interaction between the sugar and the nitrogenous base of the nucleotide, and on this basis can cause severe liver damage; necrosis, cirrhosis and cancer.

Previous research has shown that deficiencies in micronutrients such as folic acid, vitamins B₁₂, B₆, C, and E, selenium, niacin, and zinc can cause changes in DNA similar to those seen after exposure to radiation. These changes can lead to DNA double-strand breaks, oxidative lesions or both, and have been shown to be closely related to the development of cancer. However, various minerals act as protectors against the development of cancer. Among them is selenium, which stimulates the production of the enzyme glutathione peroxidase which acts to reduce hydrogen peroxide and maintain the integrity of cell membranes; and an example is zinc which acts on the processes of maintaining genomic stability and genetic expression (George, 2011).

5.4. Implications of the C677T polymorphism of the MTHFR gene in folate deficiency

Polymorphisms in genes such as Methylenetetrahydrofolate-reductase (MTHFR) and Methionine synthase (MTR) can affect the metabolism of folic acid, which can have consequences on the level of folate in the body. Folic acid deficiency can be associated with various diseases, including neural tube defects and birth defects.

The MTHFR gene codes for an enzyme called methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase. This enzyme plays a key role in the metabolism of folic acid, which is important for DNA synthesis and methylation, a process necessary to control gene expression. The MTHFR gene determines the activity of this enzyme, and mutations or polymorphisms in this gene can affect the function of the enzyme and the way the body uses folic acid metabolically. The best known and most studied mutation in the MTHFR gene is known as the C677T polymorphism. This mutation can lead to a partial deficiency of the MTHFR enzyme, resulting in a reduced ability of the body to convert folic acid into its active form, methylenetetrahydrofolate. This can result in increased levels of homocysteine in the blood, which is a risk factor for certain diseases, including heart disease. Polymorphisms in the MTHFR gene have been investigated in the context of various diseases and reactions to nutrition. Understanding the genotype for this gene can help tailor diet and nutritional supplements to ensure that people with certain polymorphisms get enough folic acid and other important nutrients (Kaput and Rodriguez, 2006).

5.5. FTO gene polymorphisms in increasing the risk of obesity

The Fat Mass and Obesity-Associated (FTO) gene is a gene that has been identified as a key factor associated with obesity. This gene plays an important role in the regulation of body mass and fat metabolism. Polymorphisms in the FTO gene are associated with an increased

risk of obesity and an increased body mass index (BMI). One of the most famous polymorphisms in the FTO gene is called rs9939609. People with certain alleles of this polymorphism have a higher risk of obesity and have a harder time maintaining a healthy body weight. Research has shown that the FTO gene affects appetite and satiety, which can lead to greater food consumption in people with certain polymorphisms of this gene. In addition, the FTO gene plays a role in regulating fat metabolism and the way the body stores and uses energy from food. However, it is important to note that the FTO gene is not the only factor influencing body mass and obesity. The interaction between genes, eating habits, level of physical activity and other factors plays a key role in the development of obesity (Kaput and Rodriguez, 2006). Obesity is the main risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, so polymorphic genes involved in the control of energy balance certainly provide a "favorable" or "unfavorable" basis for the development of coronary heart disease.

6. CONCLUSION

Genes are key factors in nutrient metabolism and individual response to nutrition. Nutrigenomics is a relatively new scientific discipline that studies the interaction between genes and nutrition and how diet can affect gene expression. This area of research opens up possibilities for personalized nutrition, which could improve health, help prevent disease, and optimize the nutritional needs of each individual. Future developments in technology and research will provide a better understanding of the genetic and nutritional factors that influence health. It is important that researchers, clinicians and society face together the challenges of nutrigenetics in order to realize its full potential for human well-being (Bouchard and Ordovas, 2012).

7. LITERATURE

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